

plexes are almost nonconducting ($\Lambda_{\infty} = 6-10 \Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$) indicating their non-ionic character.

The room temperature magnetic moment values of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes (~ 4.82 and 3.22 B.M., respectively) indicate octahedral environment of ligand molecules around spin-free Co^{II} and Ni^{II} atoms². The Cu^{II} complex displays subnormal magnetic moment value (1.51 B.M.) attributed either to copper-copper bonding or super-exchange interaction³ through sulphur atom in complex molecules. Therefore the complex is probably dimeric or polymeric.

The solid reflectance spectra of $\text{Cu}(\text{AMOPT})$ display a broad asymmetric band in the region $11\,760-14\,280 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a strong band at $23\,890 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributable to the combination of ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g} + {}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$, respectively, in tetragonal field⁴. The reflectance spectra of $\text{Co}(\text{AMOPT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ display a medium band near $17\,820-18\,520 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a shoulder near $21\,340 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The former is assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (*P*) while the latter a consequence of spin-orbit coupling in ${}^4T_{1g}$ (*P*) state⁵. In ethanol, the complex, however, shows only one broad band at $18\,150 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} 15$) in visible region attributed to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (*P*) of octahedral Co^{II} atom⁵. The reflectance spectra of $\text{Ni}(\text{AMOPT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ display a shoulder at $22\,730 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a broad medium band near $15\,870 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributable to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (*F*) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (*P*) transitions, respectively, in distorted octahedral field⁶. In solution, the complex displays these transitions as medium and broad bands at $16\,150$ ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} 18$) and at $22\,950 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} 38$).

The disappearance of ν_{OH} and ν_{SH} ligand bands at $3\,110$ and $2\,752 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively, in the ir spectra of the complexes suggests bonding of the ligand through deprotonated phenolic oxygen as well as thio sulphur. A broad band at $3\,050-3\,480 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in aquo complexes is attributed to ν_{OH} of water molecule. A strong band at $1\,592 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligand is assigned to azomethine $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ which shifted to higher frequencies by $3-15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in its complexes. The shift of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ at higher wave number in the complexes suggests the bonding of azomethine nitrogen with metal ions⁷. The ligand displays thioamide band-I at $1\,498 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which shifted to higher frequency near $1\,520-1\,537 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The thioamide band-II ($1\,278 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) also shifted to higher frequency in the complexes at $1\,280-1\,302 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The δ_{OH} of the ligand ($1\,350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) almost disappeared in the complexes indicating coordination of deprotonated phenolic oxygen. The ν_{CO} band of the ligand at $1\,260 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ shifted to higher wave numbers at $1\,290 \pm 12 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ on complexation⁸. The thioamide band-III ($1\,175 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) as expected moves to higher wave number^{9,9} by $5-25 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes. The thioamide band-IV is observed at 903 cm^{-1} and it suffered a red-shift at $680 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The red-shift⁹ of thioamide band-IV supports the bonding through deprotonated thiol sulphur.

The Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes are in general tetrahedral. The ir spectra of the Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes consist of strong and well-resolved bands while those of the octahedral Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and tetrahedral Cu^{II} complexes are ill-resolved. The difference may arise from the difference in structure of these complexes.

Analysis of ir spectral data reveals that the ligand coordinates through aldimine nitrogen (or amino nitrogen), deprotonation of OH proton, phenolic oxygen and mercapto sulphur in almost all the complexes. There is scope for bridging quadridentate mode of bonding by the ligand, leading to polynuclear species.

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Coordination Template Reactions. Part-IV. Synthesis of some Transition Metal Complexes derived from Dibenzo-(e,l)(2,3,9,10) tetraphenyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-1,3,8,10-tetraene- N_4

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METAL complexes of macrocyclic ligands have been known and some such derivatives have been prepared using phenylenediamine and related compounds¹⁻⁴. The present paper describes the template synthesis of some macrocyclic complexes of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} and Cr^{III} derived from

dibenzo(*e*, 1) (2,3,9,10) tetraphenyl-1,4,8,11-tetrazacyclotetradeca-1,3,8,10-tetraene-N₄ (TACT) (1) and their characterisation on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic, infrared and electronic spectral data.

Preparation of complexes: Benzil (0.02 mol) was dissolved in methanol containing metal salt (0.01 mol) and the solution was refluxed for 15 min. To it was added dropwise a hot solution of *m*-phenylenediamine (0.02 mol) in methanol and further refluxed for 10–15 h, till the colour of the solution turned brown. The complexes were crystallised using ether after distilling off methanol from the reaction mixture. Some of the complexes were prepared again after extricating the cyclic ligand and characterising it, in order to establish the *in situ* preparation of the complexes.

For preparing the thiocyanate complexes, ammonium thiocyanate was also added to the same solution which was being refluxed and the complexes crystallised using petroleum ether after filtering out ammonium chloride formed in the reaction.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) correspond to 1 : 1 metal–TACT stoichiometry for the complexes. The molar conductances (Λ_M) in methanol show the non-ionic nature of all the complexes except the Cr^{III} complex which is suggested to be a 1 : 1 electrolyte with two chloride ions coordinated and the third ionically held.

The μ_{eff} value (at 300 K) of the complexes corresponds to high-spin states, and the slightly weaker ligand field required for the purpose arises from the fact that the macrocyclic plane is somewhat saddle shaped with the nitrogen lone-pair pointing outside and the metal center located above the plane. As the anions are coordinated in the axial positions, all the metal ligand bonds are not equivalent and hence structure of the complexes are pseudo-octahedral.

In the infrared spectra, the stretching and deformation frequencies of the NH₂ group and the usual C=O stretch of benzil are absent and in stead a strong band at around 1600 cm⁻¹ assignable to the coordinated and conjugated C=N group⁸⁻¹¹ was observed. The additional bands attributable to the functional groups in the macrocyclic complexes such as absorptions due to benzene

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Analysis % : Found/Calcd.)		Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff}^{**} B.M.
	M	N		
[Cr(TACT)Cl ₃]Cl	6.98 (7.19)	7.34 (7.75)	83.5	3.80
[Mn(TACT)Cl ₂]	6.98 (7.97)	7.85 (8.11)	17.72	5.95
[Co(TACT)Cl ₂]	8.08 (8.48)	9.15 (8.07)	6.26	5.08
[Co(TACT)(NO ₂) ₂]	7.46 (7.88)	11.02 (11.24)	—	5.16
[Cu(TACT)Cl ₂]	8.86 (9.09)	9.99 (8.01)	13.54	2.13
[Cu(TACT)(NOS) ₂]	9.04 (8.54)	9.99 (11.29)	8.01	2.09
[Cu(TACT)(NO ₂) ₂]	8.84 (8.44)	11.54 (11.17)	17.34	2.33
[Ni(TACT)Cl ₂]	9.02 (8.50)	9.34 (8.07)	24.80	3.09
[Ni(TACT)(NOS) ₂]	7.08 (7.95)	11.09 (11.38)	13.90	3.03
[Ni(TACT)(NO ₂) ₂]	7.14 (7.88)	11.09 (11.25)	7.74	3.13

*TACT=C₄H₈N₄. **At 300 K.

ring and out-of-plane bending of phenyl groups are observed at 1590–1440 and 710–745 cm⁻¹, respectively, and remained unshifted as expected. The bands corresponding to N-bonded thiocyanate are observed at 2100–2040 cm⁻¹ and those due to coordinated chloro and nitro groups are observed at 280, 1400, 1320 and 1090 cm⁻¹, respectively¹².

In the electronic spectra of the Cr^{III} complex, three bands are observed at 36.30, 23.50, and 16.94 kK assigned to ⁴A_{2g}(P)→⁴T_{1g}(P), ⁴A_{2g}(F)→⁴T_{1g}(F) and ⁴A_{2g}(F)→⁴T_{2g}(F) transition, respectively. The spin-forbidden transition is very weak and could not be located. The values of the ratio V_2/V_1 are indicative of slightly distorted octahedral geometry¹⁴. In the electronic spectra of Mn^{II} complex no spin allowed transitions are expected, but three very weak bands are observed at 10.80, 16.52 and 24.20 kK due to ⁶A_{1g}→⁴T_{1g}(4P), ⁶A_{1g}→⁴A_g(4P) and ⁶A_{1g}→⁴A_{1g}(4G) transition, corresponding to hexacoordinated octahedral structure. The Co^{II} complexes exhibit bands due to ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{2g}(F) (ν_1), ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴A_{2g}(F) (ν_2) and ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{1g}(P) (ν_3) transitions in the range 8.13–8.40, 14.50–14.80 and 17.20–20.00 kK, respectively, characteristic of distorted octahedral geometry. The Ni^{II} complexes show three octahedral transitions, ⁸A_{2g}(F)→⁸T_{2g}(F) (ν_1), ⁸A_{2g}(F)→⁸T_{1g}(F) (ν_2) and ⁸A_{2g}(F)→⁸T_{1g}(P) (ν_3) at 12.00, 17.50 and 27.50 kK, respectively; while the Cu^{II} complexes show one or two broad maxima at 20.00–18.00 kK corresponding to two transitions, ²B_{1g}→²B_{2g} and ²B_{1g}→²E_g and suggest a distorted octahedral geometry of the complexes¹⁵.

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NaClO₄ ionic strength using Calvin – Bjerrum potentiometric titration technique.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The coumarins and their corresponding diketones were prepared by the method described earlier³. Dioxane was purified⁸. The transition metal ions were used in the form of their nitrates. A Elico LI-120 digital pH meter with an accuracy of ± 0.01 pH unit was used for pH-titrations. The pH correction factor for the non-aqueous medium was applied⁴ and the thermodynamic values reported.

The experimental setup and the method of calculations was the same as described earlier¹.

Results and Discussion

In the present investigation only one dissociation constant was obtained and is assigned to phenolic OH. The accuracy range of proton – ligand constant is ± 0.03 . The difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values of the lanthanide complexes was less than 1.78 log units indicating the simultaneous formation of both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. It was therefore decided to calculate the $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values by employing the method of least-squares⁶ (Table 1). The accuracy range of $\log K$ values is ± 0.05 log units and these values are pertaining only to conditional stability constants for the systems studied.

Plots of $\log \beta$ against pK values of the ligands were linear suggesting identical binding sites in all the ligands.

Studies on Lanthanide Metal Complexes of some Substituted-coumarins and their Corresponding Diketones

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THE present communication forms a part of our investigation of the complex formation between some physiologically active compounds belonging

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS

Cations	Ligands											
	IC		ID		IIC		IID		IIIC		IIID	
	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$										
H ⁺	9.85	—	10.25	—	8.92	—	8.70	—	9.68	—	8.60	—
La ³⁺	6.29	5.51	7.07	7.01	5.52	PPT	5.26	4.42	5.69	5.65	6.74	6.21
Pr ³⁺	6.77	6.14	7.22	7.08	5.76	PPT	5.37	5.16	6.19	5.86	7.30	7.03
Gd ³⁺	7.32	6.48	8.95	7.07	6.99	5.73	8.09	5.92	6.42	6.27	8.79	8.22
Tb ³⁺	7.52	6.31	8.21	7.16	7.49	5.78	7.02	5.31	6.62	6.03	7.61	6.90
Dy ³⁺	7.51	6.60	8.03	7.35	5.96	5.29	5.39	4.10	8.41	5.69	8.61	7.50

to lactone class and transition and lanthanide metal ions, and is in continuation with our earlier work¹. The study deals with the determination of dissociation constants of some substituted-coumarins and their corresponding diketones and stability constants of their lanthanide metal complexes in 50% (v/v) water-dioxane medium at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and 0.1 M

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